

Impact of Emotional Maturity on Inter Collegiate Badminton Players of Latur City

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Abstract:

Aims of the study to impact emotional maturity on inter collegiate Badminton players of Latur city. The samples from population of inter collegiate Badminton players selected from Mahatma Basweshwer Science College Latur, (Maharashtra), Badminton players 10 students age group under 19 years were selected through simple random sampling technique. After selection of sample, variable and tool was selected emotional maturity scale developed and standardized by Dr. Yashvir Singh and Dr. Mahesh Bhargava (2010) these inventories used for data collection. After collection of data 't' test statistical method used for described results and interpretation. Findings there is a significant difference in the emotional maturity of Badminton players.

Keywords: Emotional Maturity and Badminton players.

Introduction:

Maturation is an important variable for psychological study because it sets the ultimate limit of achievement & determines to a large degree rate of learning and enculturation. Knowledge of this development process alters physical teachers and coaches to the desirability of adopting learning situations, so that they are optimal in difficulty and complexity for the individual child. Maturation in children is occurrence with the lapse of time. Therefore chronological age is very rough approximation of the level of psychological growth for average child, when the normal range, special scales and instruments must be used to measure his maturational status. The child most difficult adjustments involve the behaviour which are the units of the social interactions are different and also the social expectations of the peer and teachers are different from those of parents and elders at home. The extent and the quality of social relationship the child maintains within a classroom determine.

Method and Material:

The study was conducted by descriptive survey method. Variable of the study include dependent variable Badminton players gender and locality and independent variable emotional maturity. Random sampling technique is used to select the sample of the population. The inter collegiate 10 Badminton players were selected randomly from Mahatma Basweshwer Science College Latur city. After selection of sample, variable and tool were selected for the collection of data which were Emotional Maturity Scale developed and standardized by Dr. Yashvir Singh and Dr. Mahesh Bhargava (2010) these records and inventories used for data collection. The students have been told to respond to the items of the questionnaires freely and frankly. After collection of data 't' test statistical method used for results and interpretation.

Results of Study:

The 't' test was used by the researcher to find out the significant difference in the

Emotional Maturity variables among Badminton players with differences in their independent and

intervening variables. The significant was set at 0.05 level of confidence.

Table No. 1: Statistical Analysis

Variables	Groups	N	df	Mean Score	SD	Mean Diff.	't'	Sig.
Emotional Maturity								
Gender	Boys	50	98	109.83	27.42	8.342	5.04	0.001
	Girls	50		101.49	24.89			
Locality	Urban area	50	98	113.36	39.54	10.960	4.58	0.002
	Rural area	50		102.37	16.83			

Figure No. 1

Result:

- There is a significant difference in emotional maturity of inter collegiate Badminton players according to the gender wise boys and girls ('t'=5.04; 2.58, 0.05 level; p=.000; P<0.05). The girls have more emotionally matured (101.49) than boys (109.83).
- There is a significant difference in the emotional maturity of inter collegiate Badminton players in urban and rural locality ('t'=4.58; 0.05 level; p=0.00; P<0.05).

Conclusion:

This study shows the nature of emotional maturity inter collegiate Badminton players in Latur city. Further this study reveals the differences influence by the demography of the players. To sustain and to increase good emotional maturity, special concern is to be extended by the parents. Parents should be met by

the teachers frequently report about students' positives and negatives and needs.

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